

Preventions Method for Child Abuse

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Abstract

Child abuse or child maltreatment is physical, sexual, and/or psychological maltreatment or neglect of a child or children, especially by a parent or other caregiver. Child abuse may include any act or failure to act by a parent or other caregiver that results in actual or potential harm to a child, and can occur in a child’s home, or in the organizations, schools or communities the child interacts with. These papers is talk about the how to prevent the child from child abuse

Introduction

Child abuse is any behavior that harms a child (in this case anyone under 18). It can take many forms, including physical, sexual and emotional abuse, as well as neglect and exploitation.

The terms child abuse and child maltreatment are often used interchangeably, although some researchers make a distinction between them, treating child maltreatment as an umbrella term to cover neglect, exploitation, and trafficking.

Different jurisdictions have developed their own definitions of what constitutes child abuse for the purposes of removing children from their families or prosecuting a criminal charge.

Types of Child Abuse

Child abuse happens when someone harms a child’s body or emotional health, development, and well-being. There are 4 main types.

- Physical abuse
- Sexual abuse
- Emotional abuse
- Neglect

Physical abuse

Any use of physical force against a child that doesn’t happen by accident and causes injury. Hitting, beating, shaking, punching, biting, burning, scratching, strangling or choking a child are all examples of child abuse.

Sexual abuse

Any type of sexual involvement or contact between a child and an adult. Sexual abuse can be voyeurism (spying on or watching a child), sexual acts and incest (sex between family members). For more information on sexual abuse, read about sexual assault.

Emotional abuse

A pattern of denying a child love, approval and security, or mistreating a child in the way an adult speaks to them or acts towards them. Bullying, yelling, isolating, criticizing, terrorizing, ignoring and shaming are all types of emotional abuse.

Neglect

Failing to provide a child with the things they need to grow, such as shelter, food, hygiene, supervision, medical attention, education or safety.

Why are children abused?

Child abuse is never okay, irrespective of the reason. Some reasons people give as to why they abuse children include:

- a desire to feel powerful and they themselves experienced abuse as children
- they don't understand that children have a right to feel safe
- They think it's okay or appropriate (it's not, ever).

Effects of Child Abuse

If you've been abused as a child, it can lead to:

- shame/self-blaming
- anger towards the abuser
- fear of getting close to and trusting people
- sadness, confusion and low self-esteem
- flashbacks, nightmares and reliving the abuse
- denial that it happened
- Trouble at school with learning new things and socializing with others.

Preventions Method for Child Abuse

A support-group structure is needed to reinforce parenting skills and closely monitor the child's well-being. Visiting home nurse or social-worker visits are also required to observe and evaluate the progress of the child and the caretaking situation.

The support-group structure and visiting home nurse or social-worker visits are not mutually exclusive. Many studies have demonstrated that the two measures must be coupled together for the best possible outcome.

Studies show that if health and medical care personnel in a structured way ask parents about important psychosocial risk factors in connection with visiting pediatric primary care and, if necessary, offering the parent help may help prevent child maltreatment.

Children's school programs regarding “good touch ... bad touch” can provide children with a forum in which to role-play and learn to avoid potentially harmful scenarios. Pediatricians can help identify children at risk of maltreatment and intervene with the aid of a social worker or provide access to treatment that addresses potential risk factors such as maternal depression.[145] Videoconferencing has also been used to diagnose child abuse in remote emergency departments and clinics.[146] Unintended conception increases the risk of subsequent child abuse, and large family size increases the risk of child neglect.[119] Thus, a comprehensive study for the National Academy of Sciences concluded that affordable contraceptive services should form the basis for child abuse prevention.

Child sexual abuse prevention programmes were developed in the United States of America during the 1970s and originally delivered to children. Programmes delivered to parents were developed in the 1980s and took the form of one-off meetings, two to three hours long. In the last 15 years, web-based programmes have been developed.

Child Abuse and the Law

Child abuse is illegal and should be reported. If you’ve been abused talk to someone you trust, who can help you through the process. You don’t have to face your abuser and talk about it in court. You can give evidence on video, without having to sit through the trauma of a court case.

Getting Help

There are things you can do to deal with child abuse and its effects.

- Talk to someone you trust about it. This could be a friend or family member. It could also be a police officer, doctor, counselor, psychologist, psychiatrist, trusted teacher, other family member or health worker.
- Remember that it’s not your fault. If you look at kids who are the same age as you were when it happened, you can understand how defenseless you were at the time.
- Learn about child abuse and its effects.
- Talk to other people who have experienced child abuse. Support groups for child abuse victims are a good place to meet other survivors who know how you feel. You don’t have to deal with this on your own.

Support Services

If you require assistance, or would like to talk to a trained professional about child abuse and how to report it please call one of these services:

- Kids Helpline on 1800 55 1800
- Lifeline on 13 11 14
- Childwise on 1800 99 10 99

Conclusion

If you see any signs of abuse in someone you know, or if you yourself are involved in an abusive relationship, get help right away. If you suspect child abuse, it’s important to report it. It isn’t a private matter or a family problem. A child’s physical and emotional well-being, and maybe even her life, could be at stake. You don’t need proof to report abuse. If you suspect it, call your local child protective services, police, a hospital, Remember that child abuse often repeats itself in the next generation. By doing what you can to prevent it today, you can help save children’s lives far into the future.

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